

Studies on biosorption of Hg^{2+} by a Hg^{2+} resistant living and non-living *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 : Characterization of some physical parameters and spectroscopic studies

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Abstract : Mercury has received considerable attention from the environmental engineers due to its high toxicity, a tendency to bio-accumulate and difficulties in its control. In present study *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* has been used as a biosorbent for Hg^{2+} biosorption due to its high Hg^{2+} tolerance and biosorption capacity. A highly Hg^{2+} resistant strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 was developed to enhance mercury biosorption. Non-living cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 was also employed for mercury biosorption and has proved to be a promising biosorbent to bring down the mercury contamination. FTIR analysis of the biosorbents reveals the involvement of -OH, C=O, -SH and other organic ligands in biosorption of Hg^{2+} ion. The effect of some important physical factors like initial Hg^{2+} ion concentration, temperature, initial pH of the medium were studied and optimized. It was found that at 30 ppm Hg^{2+} ion concentration *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 exhibited the highest biosorption capacity at 30 °C temperature and pH 5.0 of the biosorption medium.

Keywords : Mercury, biosorption, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, spectroscopic analysis, physical factors, non-living biosorbent.

Introduction

There has been increasing concern over dangerous levels of mercury, contaminating the aquatic environment and sources of potable water. This is because of the accumulation in the food chain and the persistence in nature of Hg^{2+} , when they are discharged even in small quantity by numerous industrial activities^{1,2}. Remediation of mercury contaminated waste water is generally accomplished by reverse osmosis, precipitation, evaporation, ion exchange and other physical and chemical methods^{1,3,5,6}. The potential use of microorganisms in the treatment of mercury contaminated waste water and in the recovery of metals in mining waste or in metallurgical effluents is of special importance⁴. Biosorption utilizes the ability of biological materials to accumulate heavy metals from waste stream by either metabolically, or purely physico-chemical pathways of uptake. The special surface properties of microorganisms enable them to adsorb metal ions from solution¹.

In the present study *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was the choice of biosorbent to study the biosorption of Hg^{2+} because of its easy availability and large scale cultivation

in inexpensive growth medium using relatively simple cultivation technique. The organism can be easily genetically and morphologically modified to enhance the biosorption capacity⁵⁻⁷.

The permissible limit of Hg^{2+} for heterotrophic organisms is 0.1 ppm⁸. It is observed that the Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 is much efficient than the parent strain of the organism, in withstanding Hg^{2+} toxicity.

Non-living cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 has also proved to be an efficient Hg^{2+} biosorbent. Use of non-living cells in biosorption process has some advantages e.g. low maintenance cost, no nutritional requirements, lesser chances of contamination and reuse of material.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows that Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 possess more Hg^{2+} biosorption capacity than the parent strain of the organism and the non-living Hg^{2+} resistant strain is even more efficient biosorbent for Hg^{2+} ion⁵.

Fig. 1. Comparison of Hg²⁺ biosorption capacity among the parent strain, living cells of Hg²⁺ resistant strain and dead cells of Hg²⁺ resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100

Unlike living cell, no nutrient supplement is added to the biosorption medium when dead cells are used. Chances of interfering of other metal or minerals in biosorption process are hence reduced, resulting more efficient biosorption than living cell⁵.

The FTIR spectra of Hg²⁺ exposed and Hg²⁺ unex-

posed *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (parent, living and non-living Hg²⁺ resistant strain) were compared for the determination of functional groups which may be involved in Hg²⁺ biosorption process and to investigate the reason behind the enhancement of Hg²⁺ biosorption in living and non-living Hg²⁺ resistant strain^{1-3,12,13}.

The FTIR spectra of living parent *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* without Hg²⁺ exposure shows peaks at frequency level of 3377, 1654, 1116, 914 cm⁻¹ representing -OH, C=O stretching vibration, 'C' bearing 'O' skeleton and alkyne stretching respectively (Fig. 2).

In FTIR analysis of living Hg²⁺ resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 without Hg²⁺ exposure showed peaks at 3398, 1654, 1117 and 914 cm⁻¹ representing the same ligands as described above (Fig. 3).

On exposure to 30 ppm Hg²⁺ containing medium, the Hg²⁺ resistant living *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 cell showed peaks at 3399 and 1645 cm⁻¹ wave length representing -OH and C=O group stretching vibration

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of parent *S. cerevisiae*.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of Hg^{2+} resistant *S. cerevisiae* A100.

respectively (Fig. 4).

On exposure to 35 ppm Hg^{2+} containing medium, the Hg^{2+} resistant living *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 cell showed peaks at 3406 and 1646 cm^{-1} wave length presenting the same functional groups as before (Fig. 5).

Some of the functional groups wave number shift to different extents after contact with metal solution, such as -OH from 3398 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3) to 3399 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4) and 3406 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5), C=O from 1648 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3) to 1645 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4) and 1646 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5). This is probably due to the interactions between mercury and -OH group, complexation of mercury with oxygen from the C-O bond. FTIR analysis indicates that alkyne group does not play major role in Hg^{2+} biosorption.

When dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 was exposed to 30 ppm Hg^{2+} containing aqueous solution, along with -OH and C=O groups shift of another two peaks were noticed at 1035 and 571 cm^{-1}

wave length (Fig. 6). Exposure of two more peaks indicates the availability of few more functional groups on the cell surface of the organism.

Stretching vibration for ether, ester, alcoholic group and -SH group were noticed at 1037 and 571 cm^{-1} wave length respectively when dead Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 was exposed to 35 ppm Hg^{2+} containing aqueous solution (Fig. 7).

When the living cells are autoclaved the cell wall structure is destroyed and as a result a few more functional groups are probably exposed. These may enhance the metal binding resulting in better Hg^{2+} biosorption⁵.

Fig. 8 shows the percentage of Hg^{2+} biosorption by living and dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 at different initial Hg^{2+} ion concentration ranging from 5 to 40 ppm. Percentage of biosorption increases with the increase of initial metal ion concentration upto a certain level then decreases. The increase in

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of Hg^{2+} resistant *S. cerevisiae* A100 employed for 30 ppm Hg^{2+} biosorption.

biosorption capacity of biosorbents with increase of initial metal ion concentration is probably due to higher interaction between metal ions and each biosorbent¹⁴.

For living cells maximum biosorption was observed at 30 and 35 ppm and dead cells showed maximum biosorption at 30 ppm Hg^{2+} ion concentration after which biosorption declined in both the cases.

In case of living cells, as the organism used for biosorption was 35 ppm resistant, it can grow, multiply and survive only upto 35 ppm Hg^{2+} concentration, after which the organism dies and intracellular absorption stops and total biosorption declines.

For dead cell, only cell surface adsorption takes place. At 30 ppm Hg^{2+} concentration equilibrium reached, i.e. all the free functional groups takes part in biosorption process are occupied. So beyond this particular concentration (30 ppm), percentage of biosorption drops.

From Fig. 9 it may be seen that temperature is an

important parameter for biosorption by living cell, where as the biosorption process is totally temperature independent when dead cells are used.

Temperature is important for biosorption process using living cells, as the intra-cellular metal biosorption is an energy dependent process¹. The biosorption capacity of living cell increases with the increase of temperature and it reaches maximum when the optimum temperature for the process is achieved (30 °C). Higher temperatures lead to higher affinity of metals to the binding sites of yeast surface. But when temperature is too high, there is a decrease in metal biosorption due to distortion of some sites of the cell surface available for metal biosorption⁵.

Energy independent mechanisms are less likely to be effected by temperature. Since the process responsible for biosorption by dead cells is largely physico-chemical in nature and is temperature independent⁴.

Fig. 10 indicates that 5.0 to be the optimum initial pH

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of Hg^{2+} resistant *S. cerevisiae* A100 employed for 35 ppm Hg^{2+} biosorption.

of the biosorption medium for Hg^{2+} biosorption by both living and dead Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100. A lower or higher pH resulted in decrease of biosorption rate.

At lower pH, the cell wall functional groups are closely associated with the hydronium ions (H_3O^+) and restrict the approach of metal cations as a result of repulsive force. At higher pH, hydroxo species of metals can be formed and do not bind to the adsorption sites on the surface of the adsorbents⁵.

At pH 5.0 divalent positive ions like Hg^{2+} may interact with negatively charged groups present on the biomass. On the other hand, the outer layer of the cell wall of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* consists of a coat protein, which can cause a charge through dissociation of ionizable side groups of the amino acids. The ionic states of ligands like carboxyl, phosphate, imidazole and amino groups will promote reaction with the positively charged

metal ions (Hg^{2+})^{1,4,5,15,16}. pH 5.0 as also been reported to be the optimum pH for Hg^{2+} biosorption by yeast^{4,17,18}.

The live and dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 have been used as an successful biosorbent for Hg^{2+} in the present study. Our results show that the biosorbents showed their maximum biosorption capacity at pH 5.0 and 30 °C temperature (applicable for living cells only). From FTIR spectroscopy -OH group and C=O group were found to be responsible for cell surface Hg^{2+} binding by living cell and for dead cell along with these two functional groups ether/ester/alcoholic group and -SH groups are also equally involved in biosorption. The living and dead cells used here, are capable of removing 80% and 85% Hg^{2+} ion respectively from the surrounding biosorption medium used. Use of dead Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 may be a promising technology for removing Hg^{2+} ion from waste water and industrial effluent.

Fig. 6. FTIR spectra of dead Hg^{2+} resistant *S. cerevisiae* A100 employed for 30 ppm Hg^{2+} biosorption.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Biomass preparation : *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* culture was collected from the Department of Chemical Engineering, Calcutta University, India. The biomass was maintained in YPDA (dextrose 1%, yeast extract 0.5%, peptone 0.5%, Agar 4%) medium. After 48 h growth at 30 °C temperature, pH 5.0 the culture was stored at 4 °C for biosorption of Hg^{2+} ion from surrounding medium.

Preparation of Hg^{2+} stock solution : Hg^{2+} stock solution (1000 ppm) was prepared by dissolving HgCl_2 in deionized double distilled water. Working solution of different concentration was prepared by adding the stock solution of different volume to the biosorption medium.

Development of Hg^{2+} resistant strain : *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was employed for biosorption of Hg^{2+} from a growth medium (glucose 1%, NaNO_3 0.2%, KCl 0.5%, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.5%, KH_2PO_4 0.1%, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Trace) containing different concentration of Hg^{2+} ion ranging from 5–40 ppm. The biosorption process conducted at 28 °C for 48 h. The initial pH of the biosorption medium was 5.0 adjusted with 1 : 1 HCl and 1 N NaOH solution. Inoculum volume for this experiment was 2 ml (cell density $4.2 \times 10^6/\text{ml}$).

100% of the inoculum was killed at 36 ppm Hg^{2+} containing biosorption medium (Fig. 11). Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 colony was isolated from 35 ppm Hg^{2+} containing medium by pour plate technique. The isolated Hg^{2+} resistant strain was maintained in YPD (yeast extract 0.5%, peptone 0.5%, dextrose 1%) broth and stored at 4 °C.

Preparation of non-living cells : Non-living cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 was prepared by autoclaving the living cells at 121 °C temperature, at 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min.

Analysis of Hg^{2+} : After the biosorption experiment

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of dead Hg^{2+} resistant *S. cerevisiae* A100 employed for 35 ppm Hg^{2+} biosorption

Fig. 8. Effect of initial Hg^{2+} ion concentration on Hg^{2+} biosorption by living and dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100

Fig. 9. Effect of temperature on Hg^{2+} biosorption by living and dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100

the biosorption medium was filtered through Whatman 1 filter paper and the filtrate was analysed to measure the remaining Hg^{2+} ion concentration in the solution, by mercury analyser MA5840^{1,10,11}.

A comparative study was conducted to evaluate the biosorption efficiency of the parent strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Hg^{2+} resistant strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100 and non-living cells of Hg^{2+} resistant

Fig. 10. Effect of initial pH of the biosorption medium on Hg^{2+} biosorption by living and dead cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100.

Fig. 11. % of survival and killing of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* at different Hg^{2+} ion concentration.

Saccharomyces cerevisiae A100. The same cultural conditions were applied for all three biosorbents, except non-living cells were employed in biosorption of Hg^{2+} from Hg^{2+} containing aqueous solution.

FTIR spectroscopic analysis : In order to determine the cell surface functional groups responsible for mercury biosorption, FTIR spectroscopy was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RXI FT-IR System, Model No. 54350 was used and samples were prepared as KBr discs^{1,12-15}.

Effect of physical parameters : Effect of temperature, initial metal ion concentration, initial pH of biosorption medium was observed on living and non-living cells of Hg^{2+} resistant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* A100. While conducting the experiments for evaluating the effect of a particular physical parameter, other parameters were fixed for both the biosorbents used.

Statistical analysis : The results represent the mean and standard deviation of at least three independent experiments. SD and error bars of each data are shown in the figure.

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